

STATIK NOANIQ TUTASH BALKALARNI TURLI USULLARDA HISOBLASH

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada statik noaniq balkalar turiga kiruvchi tutash balkalar hisobi kuchlar va ko'chishlar usullarida bajarilgan. Tutash balkalarda ko'chishlar usulida bajarilgan ishlar hajmi kuchlar usulida bajarilgan ishlar hajmidan ixcham ekanligi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tutash balkalar, kuchlar usuli, ko'chishlar usuli, kanonik tenglamalar sistemasi, Gauss usuli.

Tutash balkalar qurilishda, xususan ko'priklarda juda ko'p qo'llaniladi, chunki tutash balkalar statik noaniq tizimlar bo'lgani uchun ko'p proetli statik aniq tizimlardan tejamli bo'ladi hamda birorta tayanchning ishdan chiqishi inshootning butunlay buzilishiga olib kelmaydi. Tutash balkalar tayanchlaridagi ortiqcha noma'lum reaksiya kuchlarini aniqlash uchun qurilish mexanikasining bir qancha usullari mavjud. Maqolada statik noaniq tutash balkalar hisobini kuchlar va ko'chishlar usullarida bajaramiz. Statik noaniq tutash balkalar hisobini quyidagi misolda ko'ramiz. Berilgan balka uchun ko'chishlar usulining kanonik tenglamalar sistemasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\begin{cases} r_{11}z_1 + r_{12}z_2 + R_{1P} = 0, \\ r_{21}z_1 + r_{22}z_2 + R_{2P} = 0. \end{cases}$$

Balka uchun birlik va yuk epyuralarini quramiz:

Qurilgan birlik va yuk epyuralaridan foydalanib tugunlarni ajratish orqali ko'chishlar usulining kanonik tenglamalar sistemasining koeffitsientlari va ozod hadlarini aniqlaymiz:

$$r_{11}=12; r_{12}=r_{21}=2; r_{22}=10; R_{1p}=8; R_{2p}=16;$$

Bu aniqlangan qiymatlar uchun ko'chishlar usulining kanonik tenglamalar sistemasining yechimlarini olamiz:

$$\begin{cases} 12z_1 + 2z_2 + 8 = 0 \\ 2z_1 + 10z_2 + 16 = 0 \end{cases} z_1=-0.41379; z_2=-1.517241;$$

Aniqlangan ko'chishlarga ko'paytirilgan birlik epyuralar va yuk epyurasining mos ordinatalarini algebraik qo'shib yakuniy moment epyurasini olamiz.

Eguvchi moment epyurasining ordinatalari quyidagicha:

$$M_0=9.6552 \text{ KHM}; M_1=4,6896; M_2=6,8964;$$

Berilgan balka uchun kuchlar usulining kanonik tenglamalar sistemasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\begin{cases} \delta_{11}X_1 + \delta_{12}X_2 + \delta_{13}X_3 + \Delta_{1P} = 0, \\ \delta_{21}X_1 + \delta_{22}X_2 + \delta_{23}X_3 + \Delta_{2P} = 0, \\ \delta_{31}X_1 + \delta_{32}X_2 + \delta_{33}X_3 + \Delta_{3P} = 0. \end{cases}$$

Balka uchun birlik va yuk epyuralarini quramiz:

Qurilgan birlik va yuk epyuralaridan foydalanib kuchlar usulining kanonik tenglamalar sistemasining koeffitsientlari va ozod hadlarini aniqlaymiz:

$$\delta_{11} = \bar{M}_1 \times \bar{M}_1 = \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{1 \cdot 16}{2} \cdot \frac{1 \cdot 2}{3} \right] = \frac{16}{3EI};$$

$$\delta_{12} = \delta_{21} = \bar{M}_1 \times \bar{M}_2 = -\frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{3 \cdot 4}{2} \left(\frac{1 \cdot 1}{3} + \frac{0,75 \cdot 2}{3} \right) + \frac{3 \cdot 12}{2} \left(\frac{0,75 \cdot 2}{3} \right) \right] = -\frac{14}{EI};$$

$$\delta_{13} = \delta_{31} = \bar{M}_1 \times \bar{M}_3 = -\frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{3 \cdot 12}{2} \left(\frac{1 \cdot 1}{3} + \frac{0,25 \cdot 2}{3} \right) + \frac{3 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{0,25 \cdot 2}{3} \right] = -\frac{10}{EI};$$

$$\delta_{22} = \bar{M}_2 \times \bar{M}_2 = \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{3 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{3 \cdot 12}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} \right] = \frac{48}{EI};$$

$$\delta_{23} = \delta_{32} = \bar{M}_2 \times \bar{M}_3 = \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{1 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{1 \cdot 8}{2} \left(\frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{1 \cdot 1}{3} \right) + \frac{3 \cdot 8}{2} \left(\frac{3 \cdot 1}{3} + \frac{1 \cdot 2}{3} \right) + \frac{3 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{1 \cdot 2}{3} \right] = \frac{112}{3EI};$$

$$\delta_{33} = \bar{M}_3 \times \bar{M}_3 = \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{3 \cdot 12}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{3 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} \right] = \frac{48}{EI};$$

$$\Delta_{1P} = \bar{M}_1 \times M_P = \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{28 \cdot 4}{2} \left(\frac{1 \cdot 1}{3} + \frac{0,75 \cdot 2}{3} \right) + \frac{6 \cdot 4^3}{12} \left(\frac{1 \cdot 1}{2} + \frac{0,75 \cdot 1}{2} \right) \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{3EI} \left[\frac{28 \cdot 12}{2} \cdot \frac{0,75 \cdot 2}{3} - \frac{32 \cdot 12}{2} \cdot \frac{0,75 \cdot 1}{3} \right] = \frac{332}{3EI};$$

$$\Delta_{2P} = \bar{M}_2 \times M_P = \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{28 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} - \frac{6 \cdot 4^3}{12} \cdot \frac{3}{2} - \frac{28 \cdot 12}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{32 \cdot 12}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 1}{3} \right] = -\frac{304}{EI};$$

$$\Delta_{3P} = \bar{M}_3 \times M_P = \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{28 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{1 \cdot 2}{3} - \frac{6 \cdot 4^3}{12} \cdot \frac{1}{2} - \frac{28 \cdot 8}{2} \left(\frac{1 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{3 \cdot 1}{3} \right) + \frac{12 \cdot 8}{2} \left(\frac{1 \cdot 1}{3} + \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} \right) \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{12 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{32 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot 1}{3} \right] = -\frac{16}{EI};$$

Bu aniqlangan qiymatlar uchun ko'chishlar usulining kanonik tenglamalar sistemasining yechimlarini olamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{16}{3} X_1 - 14 X_2 - 10 X_3 + \frac{332}{3} = 0 \\ -4 X_1 + 48 X_2 + \frac{112}{3} X_3 - 304 = 0 \\ -10 X_1 + \frac{112}{3} X_2 + 48 X_3 - 16 = 0 \end{cases}$$

Algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini Gauss usuli bilan yechib (Gauss jadvali keltirilmagan), noma'lumlarning qiymatlari aniqlanadi:

$$X_1 = -9,655177 \text{ kNm}; X_2 = 12,206893 \text{ kN}; X_3 = -11,172412 \text{ kN}.$$

Topilgan qiymatlardan foydalanib yakuniy moment epyurasi quriladi. Qurilgan yakuniy epyura yuqorida ko'chishlar usulida olingan epyura bilan aynan bo'ladi. Deformatsion tekshiruvni bajaramiz:

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{EI} \left[-\frac{9.6552}{2} \left(\frac{16 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{12}{3} \right) + \frac{6 \cdot 4^3}{12} \left(\frac{16}{2} + \frac{12}{2} \right) - \frac{4.6896 \cdot 4}{2} \left(\frac{16 \cdot 1}{3} + \frac{12 \cdot 2}{3} \right) - \frac{4.6896}{2} \left(\frac{12 \cdot 2}{3} + \frac{4 \cdot 1}{3} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{EI} \left[\frac{6.8964 \cdot 8}{2} \left(\frac{12 \cdot 1}{3} + \frac{4 \cdot 2}{3} \right) + \frac{6.8964 \cdot 2}{2} \cdot \frac{4 \cdot 2}{3} - \frac{32 \cdot 4}{2} \cdot \frac{4 \cdot 1}{3} \right] = 0.00032;$$

Tutash balkalarda ko'chishlar usulida bajarilgan ishlar hajmi kuchlar usuli hajmidan ixcham, shuning uchun tutash balkalarda ko'chishlar usulini qo'llash maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

Adabiyotlar:

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